

Low-temperature discharging performance comparison of sodium-ion and lithium-ion cylindrical batteries

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Abstract

This work presents a systematic comparison of the low-temperature discharge performance of cylindrical sodium-ion (SIB) and lithium-ion (LIB) batteries in the 18650 format. Two commercial SIB cells, designed for high-energy and high-power applications, were evaluated alongside three LIB chemistries: nickel–manganese–cobalt oxide (NMC), lithium iron phosphate (LFP), and lithium titanate (LTO). Constant current discharge tests were conducted at temperatures from 25 to -40 °C to assess capacity, energy, power, and thermal behavior. At room temperature, NMC-based LIBs exhibited the highest energy density, but their usability ends below -20 °C. LFP and LTO cells retained at least partial functionality at -30 °C but failed at lower temperatures. This behavior is also similar for SIB high-energy cells, whereas the high-power variant maintained stable discharge across all tested rates to -30 °C and retained usable capacity even at -40 °C. These results demonstrate that although SIBs possess lower energy density than LIBs at ambient conditions, their superior resilience in extreme cold (≤ -20 °C) makes them promising candidates for cold climate applications.

Graphical abstract

Keywords Batteries · Lithium ion · Sodium ion · Electrochemistry · Kinetics

Introduction

Reliable battery performance in low-temperature environments is critical for various applications, such as space missions, outdoor systems, and operations in cold climates [1]. Nevertheless, at low temperatures, lithium-ion batteries (LIBs) exhibit significant performance limitations, typically manifested as large overpotentials and severely reduced

energy due to hindered Li^+ transport within the cell. Furthermore, electrolyte freezing is expected below -30 °C for commonly used LiPF_6 in ethylene carbonate/ethyl methyl carbonate solvents [2]. Efforts to improve the low-temperature performance of LIBs focus primarily on electrolyte and electrode engineering, targeting issues like ion desolvation and charge-transfer resistance at the electrode–electrolyte interface. Strategies include using low freezing point solvent mixtures, EC-free electrolytes, and engineered solid electrolyte interphases (SEI) to enhance Li^+ mobility [1]. In this context, it is noteworthy that ether-based electrolytes, despite their attractive low-temperature transport properties, were historically excluded from commercial LIB systems because of their limited upper (oxidative) stability window

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and structural damage caused by ether/Li⁺ co-intercalation in graphite [3].

Another approach to achieving efficient low-temperature performance in energy storage systems is to adopt an alternative technology that exhibits more favorable behavior under such conditions. One promising candidate is the recently commercialized sodium-ion battery (SIB). Here, “SIB” denotes a technology platform encompassing multiple cell chemistries (e.g., layered transition metal oxides, polyanionic compounds, and Prussian blue analogs as cathode families), which can differ markedly in performance and operating limits [4]. In general, SIBs offer the potential for lower cost and reduced dependence on critical materials, as they use the more abundant sodium and can employ aluminum instead of copper as the anode current collector [5]. Additionally, some manufacturers report lower operational temperature limits compared to those typical for LIBs. This improved behavior may be explained by the fact that, although SIBs suffer from sluggish Na⁺ diffusion at low temperatures, Na⁺ ions can desolvate more easily than Li⁺ ions, potentially enabling faster interfacial reactions, such as charging and discharging, under cold conditions [6]. Moreover, in SIBs, ether-based electrolytes have regained strong interest due to their kinetic advantages and low-temperature suitability, including cases where solvated Na⁺ co-intercalation can enable sodium storage in graphite in glyme-based electrolytes. Recent ether-electrolyte designs for SIBs explicitly target sub-zero operation by leveraging very low freezing point ether components (e.g., tetrahydrofuran) and modified solvation to depress electrolyte freezing to below −60 °C [7].

Beyond low-temperature cell performance, SIBs have also been reported to exhibit reduced inhomogeneities in parallel configurations under resistance-driven mismatch when compared with LIB chemistries (lithium iron phosphate (LFP) and nickel cobalt aluminum (NCA)): for an added contact resistance up to 25 mΩ, the maximum state-of-charge drift reaches ~15% for LFP, while NCA and the investigated SIB reach ~4% and ~2%, respectively [8]. Complementary work shows that current inhomogeneity scales with path-resistance inhomogeneity and saturates with increasing parallelization, providing a framework to extrapolate mismatch effects to higher parallel cell counts [9]. As monitoring per-path currents in parallel operation is noted to be challenging for the battery management system due to sensor cost/complexity, intrinsically smaller resistance-driven inhomogeneities can be advantageous for battery systems designed with limited electronics.

Accordingly, systematic performance benchmarking of commercial SIB cells has become a central research focus. Dorau et al. conducted a comprehensive structural and electrochemical analysis of four commercial SIBs, revealing considerable variation in electrode coatings, particle sizes, and

cathode materials, and highlighting the critical role of these design factors for performance and degradation, particularly at low temperatures down to 0 °C [10]. Similarly, Marangon et al. systematically investigated 18650-type SIB cells with layered oxide cathodes and hard carbon (HC) anodes, concluding that while sluggish Na⁺ kinetics at the anode remain a bottleneck, the overall cell performance is already getting close to certain types of LFP-based LIBs [11]. Rehm et al. directly compared commercial SIBs with layered oxide cathodes to state-of-the-art LFP cells within a 10–45 °C window, showing that although SIBs exhibit a stronger dependence of impedance and efficiency on temperature and state of charge, their C-rate capability is on par with the investigated LFP cells [12]. Thus, case-by-case comparisons have shown that SIB cells can approach, or in certain metrics even surpass, LFP-based LIB cells in terms of specific performance indicators. Nevertheless, their behavior at sub-zero temperatures, particularly in direct comparison with LIBs, remains largely unexplored, leaving uncertainty over the prospective applicability of this technology in cold environments.

Consequently, in this work, two 18650 cylindrical SIB cells, high-energy and high-power variants with layered metal oxide-based cathodes, are systematically evaluated and compared with three LIB cells of the same format utilizing different chemistries. Constant current discharge tests are conducted to investigate their performance in terms of available capacity, energy, and temperature rise in order to assess their application potential at low and sub-zero temperatures.

Results and discussion

The performance of the cells is described in terms of their provided capacity, energy, average power, and experienced temperature increase within the CC discharge at the target conditions. These results are visualized in Fig. 1. For each case, two cell samples were tested. The bar represents the average value of the two cells, while the error bar indicates the range between the individual measurements.

The overall capacity and energy levels at 25 °C for each chemistry correspond to the values listed in Table 1. Among them, LIB NMC exhibits the highest volumetric and gravimetric energy density, significantly surpassing the other chemistries in terms of capacity, energy, and power. Since its rated capacity is roughly twice that of the others, the absolute discharge currents at the corresponding C-rates are also higher. As a result, the cells achieve very high power mainly through high discharge currents, with higher voltage levels playing a smaller role. These high currents, however, also drive the strong heat generation and temperature rise. At 25 °C, this gets close to being performance limiting: the cell surface temperature reached 60 °C, triggering the safety cutoff by temperature before the voltage limit was reached.

Fig. 1 The measurement results summarizing the achieved capacity, energy, average power, and temperature increase across all the CC discharge tests

A strong temperature rise was also observed at low ambient temperatures, which effectively improved performance by warming the cells internally. For example, at $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, the cells warmed up to $-8.6\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ during 0.3 C and 1 C discharges, respectively. In terms of low-temperature operation, LIB NMC remained operable at 0.3 C and 1 C discharges at $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. However, at higher C-rates and/or lower ambient temperatures, the delivered energy fell below the inoperable threshold.

At the opposite end of the spectrum for capacity, energy, and power is LIB LTO, which exhibits the lowest values. The first performance limitation was observed in one cell during a 3 C discharge at $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. At $-30\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, only about a quarter of the reference energy could be achieved at 0.3 C, resulting in limited performance. At lower temperatures or higher rates, the cells became inoperable.

LIB LFP is positioned between NMC and LTO in terms of performance, and at warmer temperatures it outperforms

Table 1 Overview of the investigated battery cells

Cell type	SIB HE	SIB HP	LIB NMC	LIB LFP	LIB LTO
Manufacturer	Hakadi	Hakadi	LG	JGNE	Huahui Energy
Nominal capacity/Ah	1.5	1.3	3.5	1.8	1.3
Nominal voltage/V	3.1	3.0	3.6	3.2	2.4
Volumetric energy density/Wh/l	281	236	762	348	189
Gravimetric energy density/Wh/kg	126	98	257	139	81
Cathode material	$\text{Na}_x\text{Ni}_{1/3}\text{Fe}_{1/3}\text{Mn}_{1/3}\text{O}_2$	$\text{Na}_x\text{Ni}_{1/3}\text{Fe}_{1/3}\text{Mn}_{1/3}\text{O}_2$	$\text{LiNi}_{0.8}\text{Mn}_{0.1}\text{Co}_{0.1}\text{O}_2$	LiFePO_4	$\text{LiCo}_{0.85}\text{Mn}_{0.15}\text{O}_2$
Anode material	HC	HC	Gr-Si	Gr	$\text{Li}_4\text{Ti}_5\text{O}_{12}$

the SIB cells. The decline of capacity and energy with decreasing temperature is more pronounced than in other LIB chemistries. The two tested cells exhibited heterogeneous behavior: one cell became inoperable already at -10°C at the highest C-rates (2.4 C and 3 C), and at -20°C for 1.7 and 2.4 C (neither cell performed at 3 C), while the other remained operable without limitations. This discrepancy can most likely be attributed to manufacturing-related cell-to-cell variations. Small differences in composition and structure have little effect under nominal conditions, but at extreme conditions, such as very low temperatures combined with high currents, they become significantly more pronounced, leading to reliability issues. At -30°C , one cell still showed limited performance at 0.3 C, but beyond this point, neither cell was able to discharge further at such low temperatures.

For SIBs, the HE cells deliver higher capacity and energy, as expected, due to their larger capacity than SIB HP cells and consequently higher absolute current values, as well as higher average power at warmer temperatures. The first inoperability for SIB HE was observed at -20°C with a 3 C discharge. At a further 10°C lower ambient temperature, only a 0.3 C-limited discharge was possible; beyond this point, the cells became inoperable.

In contrast, SIB HP cells demonstrated stable discharge performance across the entire current range down to -30°C . At -40°C , a discharging performance limitation occurred, and one cell showed reliability issues at 1.7 C. At this temperature, higher C-rates were not feasible for either cell.

To compare the batteries in terms of energy at the lowest applied current in this study, i.e., 0.3 C, representing often the nominal rate at electric vehicle applications, Fig. 2a is provided. The figure highlights the clear superiority of NMC LIB over all other investigated chemistries down to -20°C . Among the remaining cells, LFP delivers the highest energy down to its operational temperature limit of -20°C . Beyond this point, one of the LFP cells exhibits reliability issues and is surpassed by the SIBs, with SIB HP taking the lead. Notably, SIB HP is the only chemistry that continues at least partial operability down to -40°C . When considering

Fig. 2 The energy available with (a) 0.3 C and (b) 1 C discharges for the tested cells

discharge at 1 C, as illustrated in Fig. 2b, SIB HP is the only technology that supports full operability at -30°C and with limited discharging performance also at -40°C .

The characterization and performance comparison show that the discharge capability of SIBs differs significantly at the lowest temperatures, despite their identical electrode chemistry. This indicates that the structural design and other factors, defining the cells as HE or HP, play a crucial role. The detailed 0.3 C discharge profiles for SIB HE are presented in Fig. 3, where stronger temperature dependence and a larger voltage drop, caused by higher resistance, can

Fig. 3 The 0.3 C discharge voltage profiles for SIB HE

Fig. 4 The 0.3 C discharge voltage profiles for SIB HP

be observed compared to SIB HP under similar conditions (Fig. 4).

Selected performance indicators are summarized in Fig. 5. Overall, in terms of capacity, energy, and power, LIBs, particularly NMC and LFP, showed better discharge performance down to $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. Under restricted conditions and at low currents, LFP and LTO remained operable even at $-30\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, with SIB HE performing similarly, though slightly better. In contrast, SIB HP proved to be a strong candidate for low-temperature operation, maintaining full operability down to $-30\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and limited performance, but still usable, even at $-40\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. Temperature rise is typically viewed as undesirable because it reflects resistive losses and increases the burden on the thermal management system. However, at low ambient temperatures, the associated self-heating can be advantageous, partially offsetting kinetic limitations by warming the cell toward more favorable operating conditions. Importantly, part of the observed low-temperature operability, particularly at higher C-rates,

may therefore be enabled by internal heat generation during discharge, rather than reflecting intrinsically favorable low-temperature electrochemical kinetics alone. Consequently, performance at high C-rates should be interpreted as a combined effect of electrochemical behavior and resistive self-heating under load, whereas low-rate behavior more directly reflects intrinsic low-temperature robustness.

This study shows that some SIB cells, especially power-oriented designs, deliver better low-temperature discharge performance than the tested LIBs, and they work over a wider range of low-temperature conditions. In practice, this can either give better performance with the same system design or reduce the need for battery heating (less preheating, smaller heaters), which lowers cost and complexity and improves cold-start reliability. Based on these comparative trends under the present test protocol, potential use cases include applications in cold climate regions, such as outdoor consumer devices, remote sensors and telemetry, telecommunications, light electric vehicles, and stationary energy storage systems, and may extend to selected aerospace-relevant use cases, subject to system-level validation.

Conclusion

This work compared the low-temperature discharge behavior of five 18650 cells, two SIBs (HE, HP) and three LIBs (NMC, LFP, LTO), under constant current tests. At $25\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, the NMC LIB delivered the highest energy and power but was limited by heat generation at high current and lost operability below $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. LFP and LTO remained only partially usable at $-30\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and then only at low current, which was also the case for SIB HE. By contrast, SIB HP maintained functionality down to $-40\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, albeit with reduced output. These results indicate that suitably designed SIBs can be a promising alternative for operation in extreme cold ($\leq -20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$) environments. The application implications are therefore prospective and inferred from cell-level trends, and should be verified for specific duty cycles and environments at the module/system level.

From an application perspective, SIBs can reduce preheating needs and simplify thermal management for systems that must start and run in cold climates, provided their lower energy density around $0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and above is acceptable. Technology selection should therefore be made at the system level, weighing cell performance together with thermal, electrical, and cost constraints.

Future work should quantify power capability and impedance as a function of state of charge to assess cold-start behavior more rigorously. Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy, in particular, can clarify mass-transport and charge-transfer limitations. Mapping impedance together with self-heating will inform thermal management design,

Fig. 5 Spider plot comparing six selected performance metrics of the tested cells. The lowest operational temperature is defined as the coldest ambient at which the cell delivers $\geq 50\%$ of its 25 °C energy at 1 C

which will help in quantifying the needed performance. In addition, charging behavior and its limits at low temperature warrant dedicated study, since charging is typically permitted only at temperatures about 20–30 °C higher than those acceptable for discharge.

Experimental

For this study, five types of 18650 cylindrical battery cells were used, and the summary of their parameters is presented in Table 1. Among the tested cells, there are two SIB cells, one designed as high energy (HE), and the other as high power (HP). Additionally, three LIB cell types utilizing chemistries based on nickel–manganese–cobalt (NMC), LFP, and lithium titanate oxide (LTO) were used. The data in Table 1 were derived from corresponding datasheets [13–17], except electrode material information, which was determined by cell disassembly and measurement on the electrodes via TESCAN VEGA 3 LMU, a scanning electron microscope (SEM) with energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS).

Battery testing was conducted using a Neware BTS4000-5V12A tester, while the cells were placed during the experiment in a thermally controlled environment in the chambers of Weiss WT3 600/70 and Memmert ICP260+. For each test, two cells of the same type were used to ensure repeatability and highlight heterogeneity or reliability issues linked

to the performance. However, this limited sample size does not allow robust statistical inference; therefore, the results and conclusions are intended to highlight qualitative and comparative trends (operability categories and relative performance versus temperature/C-rate) rather than population-level statistics.

At first, a preconditioning test was applied to each of the cells, which consisted of five nominal cycles, in order to stabilize the electrochemical performance of the cells. Subsequently, the capacity tests were performed with defined currents and at defined temperatures. The specific procedure of the capacity tests consisted of ‘calibrated’ charging at 25 °C in constant current–constant voltage (CCCV) mode, where the constant current of 0.5 C was used to achieve the respective voltage limits, and the charging continued at the constant voltage until the current dropped below $C/30$. Afterward, the cells were brought to and stabilized at the target temperature (25, 0, –10, –20, –30, and –40 °C) to be discharged with the target constant current (CC) (0.3, 1, 1.7, 2.4, 3 C). The LIB NMC maximum current was limited only to 2.85 C, i.e., 10 A, to not exceed the datasheet’s limits.

To provide a tangible operational metric, the following methodology was applied to assess whether a cell was fully, partially, or not operable under a given test condition. A cell was classified as operable when it delivered more than 50% of the discharge energy obtained at 25 °C and 1 C (the threshold shown as a solid line in Fig. 1). When the delivered energy was below this limit but above 10% of the

reference energy (this limit is marked by a dotted line in Fig. 1), the cell was classified as performance-limited. If the delivered energy was below 10% of the reference energy, the cell was classified as inoperable. When two replicate cells exhibited markedly different behavior under the same conditions (e.g., one operable and the other inoperable), this was reported as a reliability or heterogeneity issue.

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Declarations

Conflict of interest The authors have no competing interests to declare that are relevant to the content of this article.

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